

Potentiometric Study of the Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Uranyl(II) with 3-Hydroxy Naphthalene-2-Carboxylic Acid

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The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) with 3-hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid have been determined at 30°, 35° and 40° in dioxane-water medium (70% V/V) and at ionic strength 0.1M(KNO₃) using Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values of the chelates have also been calculated using temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation.

3-Hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid is an efficient complexing agent. Its complexes with different metal ions have been studied earlier by various workers, under different experimental conditions¹⁻⁵. Makitie⁴ has studied the formation of chelate of 3-hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid with Zn(II) in aqueous solution by potentiometric and by spectrophotometric methods. Desai² has studied the chelation of UO₂(II) with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid by spectrophotometric method.

The results of potentiometric study of complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) with 3-hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid at 30°, 35° and 40° in dioxane-water medium (70%V/V) and at ionic strength 0.1M(KNO₃) using Calvin-Bjerrum^{6,7} pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸ are being reported. The study reveals the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The values of overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have also been evaluated. Attempts to study complexation with Hg(II) resulted in failure because of its precipitation at very low pH.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B. D. H. AnalaR quality. The double distilled CO₂ free water was used in all experimental work. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in double distilled water and standardized by standard volumetric methods. pH was measured on a digicord pH meter having a sensitivity of ± 0.002 and was calibrated by suitable buffers before use. The thermostat bath temperatures were maintained at 30° $\pm 0.1^\circ$, 35° $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and 40° $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and the titrations were carried out in (50%V/V) dioxane-water mixture.

The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows :

- A : 1.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M HNO₃, B : 1.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M HNO₃
+ 5.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M ligand
C : 1.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M HNO₃ + 5.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M ligand
+ 1.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M metal ion solution,

such that the concentrations of common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of KNO₃ (1.0M) was added to maintain 0.1M ionic strength. The above solutions were titrated against standard KOH solution prepared in 70% dioxane-water mixture. Three titration curves were obtained which were referred to as (i) acid titration curve. (ii) ligand titration curve. (iii) complex titration curve.

The concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations.

Results and Discussion

\bar{n}_H , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by employing the relationships derived by Irving and Rossotti⁹.

The practical proton-ligand stability constant, $\log^p K_1^H$ was obtained from the proton-ligand formation curve plotted between \bar{n}_H vs pH, as Bjerrum's half-integral value at 1.5 \bar{n}_H . The same has also been calculated by pointwise calculation method using the following equation :

$$\log^p K_1^H = \text{pH} + \log (\bar{n}_H - 1) / (2 - \bar{n}_H)$$

(for all points above $\bar{n}_H = 1$)

In case of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid, since there are very few values of \bar{n}_H below one, the value of $\log^p K_1^H$ has been obtained by using the following relationship :

$$\log^p K_1^H - \log^p K_2^H = 2\text{pH} \quad (\text{at } \bar{n}_H = 1)$$

Metal-ligand stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated from the formation curves obtained by plotting graphs between \bar{n} and pL, using Bjerrum's half-integral method⁷, pointwise calculation or interpolation at various \bar{n} values and graphical method⁹, and extended to dioxane-water mixture by Van Uitert and Haas¹⁰. In case of UO₂(II) complex, since there are very few values of \bar{n} below one, the value of $\log K_1$ was obtained by interpolation at midpoint using the following relationship :

$$\log K_1 K_2 = 2 \text{pL} \quad (\text{at } \bar{n} = 1)$$

TABLE I—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND. STEPWISE AND OVERALL METAL-LIGAND STABILITY COMPLEXES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT THREE TEMPERATURES.

Cation	Constants	Temperature			$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kcal/mole ⁻¹)			ΔH° (kcal mole ⁻¹) at 35°	ΔS° (cal mole ⁻¹ degree ⁻¹) at 35°
		30°	35°	40°	30°	35°	40°		
H(I)	$\log^p K_1^H$	5.70	5.45	5.10					
	$\log^p K_2^H$	2.50	2.55	2.60					
	$\log^p \beta_3^H$	8.20	8.00	7.70					
Z(II)	$\log K_1$	2.65 (2.11)	2.62 (2.07)	2.57 (1.98)					
	$\log K_2$	2.61 (3.17)	2.57 (3.17)	2.54 (3.16)					
	$\log \beta_2$	5.26	5.19	5.11	7.29	7.31	7.32	-6.2	3.5
Cd(II)	$\log K_1$	2.40 (1.78)	2.39 (1.76)	2.36 (1.72)					
	$\log K_2$	2.47 (3.14)	2.46 (3.15)	2.45 (3.15)					
	$\log \beta_2$	4.87	4.85	4.81	6.75	6.83	6.89	-2.5	14.1
UO ₂ (II)	$\log K_1$	7.28	7.10	7.06					
	$\log K_2$	3.94	3.93	3.79					
	$\log \beta_2$	11.22	11.03	10.85	15.55	15.54	15.54	-15.4	0.5

Bracketed are the values refined by the method of successive approximations. In case of UO₂(II), this method is not applicable since the value, 0.5n is not available.

The mean values of protonation constants and formation constants are reported in Table I. Since the ratio of successive constants is less than 10⁴ i. e. $K_1/K_2 < 10^4$, therefore the method of successive approximations⁹ was used to refine the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in all cases except UO₂(II), for which the value of pL at 0.5 \bar{n} could not be found. Since the formation curve for UO₂(II) system starts at a value above $\bar{n} = 0.5$.

The error limits vary from ± 0.01 to ± 0.05 for $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values of stability constants.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complexation have been determined using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation¹¹ (Table I).

The precision of ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° values are ± 0.08 kcal mole⁻¹, ± 0.1 kcal mole⁻¹ and ± 0.3 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively. In case of Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) chelates with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid \bar{n} values approach a value of 2, indicating the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The data show a decrease in the values of overall protonation constants and formation constants with increase of temperature. Generally the value of $\log K_2$ is less than that of $\log K_1$ on account of statistical and electrostatic factors¹². In the present case the value of $\log K_2$ is slightly greater than that of $\log K_1$ in case of Cd(II) complex with 3-hydroxy naphthalene-2-carboxylic acid at all the three temperatures investigated. The stereochemical change from octahedral to tetrahedral complex appears to be responsible for this additional stability. The free

energies of formation (ΔG°) of the complexes have more negative values with the increase of temperature, showing that complex formation is a spontaneous process. Both enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes favour the formation of complexes.

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